

Functionalized triarylamine for applications in organic electronics[†]

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Abstract : Over the last few decades significant progress has been made in the field of organic electronics which includes Organic light emitting diodes (OLEDs), Organic field effect transistors (OFETs) and Dye sensitized solar cells (DSSCs). Small organic π -conjugated molecules with a donor-acceptor (D-A) architecture have attracted significant attention as compared to polymers. In organic electronics, typically an OLED consists of a hole-transporting materials (HTMs) (*p*-type materials) and electron-transporting material (ETMs) (*n*-type materials). The efficiency and durability of organic electronic devices depend upon the stability of both the hole and electron-transporting materials. Triarylamine derivatives have been extensively utilized as both hole transporter and emissive material in opto-electronics, since they exhibit low ionization potential, reversible redox potential and bright fluorescence and very few reports are there for triarylamine as *n*-type materials. In this paper, triarylamine based D-A molecules are discussed for their possible applications as *n*-type and/or *p*-type and ambipolar materials in organic electronics.

Keywords : Organic electronics, Triarylamine derivatives, hole transportation, ambipolar materials.

n-Type materials

Tremendous success have been achieved in the development of *p*-type materials, but development of *n*-type of materials is still lagging far behind than *p*-type of materials, hence there is a need for the development of high mobility and environmentally stable electron transporting materials. The *n*-type materials play the role of facilitating electron injection from the cathode into the organic layer. Materials which have high electron affinities together with high ionization potentials usually function as electron transporting materials i.e. materials with electron accepting properties are serve as *n*-type materials¹. Common approach in the development of electron transporting materials is the introduction of electron withdrawing groups such as carbonyl, cyano and per-fluorinated alkyl chains to *p*-type of materials. Another approach is the substitution with a more electro-negative atom of a carbon in an extended π -system of organic mol-

ecules. The low LUMO energy levels (LUMO value between -3.0 to -4.0 eV)¹ are essential for the efficiency and stability of electron transporting (*n*-type) materials¹. Fig. 1 shows commonly used *n*-type materials.

Recently we have synthesized certain triarylamine based on naphtho[2,3-*f*]quinoxaline-7,12-dione core as donor-acceptors for *n*-type materials (Fig. 2)^{2,3}. Absorption spectra of all the synthesized molecules showed an intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) transitions in the range of 405–561 nm. Electrochemical properties of the compounds were studied by cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse voltammetry. The HOMO and LUMO energy levels are in the range of -4.88 to -5.57 eV and -3.37 to -3.48 eV respectively.

Low-lying LUMO energy levels of these molecules are comparable to well-known electron transporter

[†]Invited Lecture.

Fig. 1. A sample of *n*-type materials with high electron affinity for organic devices.

Fig. 2. Molecular structure of triarylamines based on naphtho[2,3-*f*]quinoxaline-7,12-diones.

materials and make them potential candidates as *n*-type materials and are thermally stable.

p-Type materials

Materials which have low ionization potentials together with low electron affinities usually function as Hole Transporting Materials (HTMs) (*p*-type of materials). The hole transport layer in a multilayer de-

vice facilitates hole injection from the anode and transport the injected holes to the emitting layer. Therefore, an ideal hole-transporting material should undergo reversible anodic oxidation to form stable cation radicals and should possess high hole mobilities. Most widely used HTMs of the triarylamine family in OLEDs are TPD, α -NPD and spiro-OMe-TAD (Fig. 3). However, TPD and α -NPD, which have low glass

Fig. 3. Commonly used *p*-type of materials.

5.35 eV and -2.75 to -3.17 eV respectively with electrochemical bandgap within the range of 2.12–2.45 eV. HOMO energy levels of synthesized compounds are comparable with most commonly used hole transporting materials such as TPD, α -NPD and spiro-OMe-TAD etc. and thus make them potential candidates for the hole transporting material in organic electronics.

Ambipolar materials

Organic molecules that display both hole and electron transporting properties are called as ambipolar organic semiconductors. This may be achieved through the use of a bilayer or blend of semiconductor materials, one *p*-type and one *n*-type⁶. Ambipolar trans-

Fig. 4. Molecular structures of dibenzo[a,c]phenazine and tribenzo[a,c,i]phenazine derivatives.

transition temperature (T_g) of 65°C and 95°C , respectively, tend to crystallize or expand during device fabrication and hence there is a need for new thermally stable HTMs.

Our group recently synthesized triaryl amines based on phenazine derivatives with good thermal stability^{4,5} (Fig. 4). The HOMO and LUMO energy levels of phenazine derivatives are in the range of -5.03 to $-$

port prevails when molecules have HOMO levels > -5.6 eV and LUMO levels < -3.15 eV⁷. Very recently (2017) we have synthesized Anthraquinone Amine-Based D-A derivatives (Fig. 5) as an ambipolar material⁸. The HOMO and LUMO energy levels of synthesized compounds are found in the range of -5.18 to -5.79 eV and -3.22 to -3.53 eV respectively as calculated by CV.

Fig. 5. Molecular structures of anthraquinone amine-based D-A derivatives.

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